

LASER-INDUCED STRENGTHENING OF SOFT ROCKS: MECHANISMS AND APPLICATIONS IN BOREHOLE STABILIZATION

student Zewei Li, associate professor Xiaowei Feng

School of Mines, China University of Mining and Technology,

Xuzhou, 221116, China

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Abstract : This study investigates the effects of laser irradiation on the mechanical properties and microstructure of soft rocks (sandstone, mudstone, and coal) through experiments combining XRD, SEM, CT, and Brazilian splitting tests. Results demonstrate that laser treatment significantly enhances rock strength, with saturated specimens exhibiting higher peak loads than dry ones due to hydrothermal coupling effects. By adjusting laser parameters and employing high-pressure gas assistance, a high-strength vitreous casing can be formed on borehole walls. The findings reveal the dual potential of laser irradiation for both rock fracturing and repair, providing theoretical support for next-generation borehole stabilization technologies in deep underground engineering.

Kalit so'zlar: Lazer nurlanishi; Tosh; Quduqning barqarorligi; Mexanik xususiyatlar;

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1. Introduction

The earliest records of laser burning of rock date back to 1960s [1]. Laser irradiation of rock mass has been used in recent decades for oil-gas drilling or hard rock excavation [2]. Most studies have focused on the cracking characteristics of laser irradiation, and rarely on the strengthening effect of the rock.

This study takes typical soft rocks (sandstone, mudstone, coal) as the research objects. Through laser irradiation experiments, supplemented by a variety of testing methods, it provides some insights into the basic control of laser-assisted excavation in deep underground engineering.

2. Materials and Methods

Three soft rocks (sandstone, mudstone, coal) were selected. Disk specimens (50 mm diameter, 25 mm height) underwent laser ablation under varying parameters.

The testing methods include: XRD analysis for mineral phase transformation, SEM for observing the microstructure, and CT scanning for reconstructing the three-dimensional cavity distribution; for the mechanical tests, the Brazilian splitting test was adopted, and DIC strain field monitoring was carried out simultaneously.

3. Results

3.1 Mechanical Behavior

Laser-treated specimens showed increased peak loads (e.g., saturated mudstone: 7.64 kN vs. untreated: 7.12 kN). The strength of the saturated specimens was even higher than that of the dry specimens (e.g., mudstone specimen: M-7-W vs. M-1-D), which breaks through the traditional understanding of water weakening[3]. DIC revealed that the crack paths of the laser-treated specimens were concentrated on the periphery of the circular ablation zone, forming a "strengthening barrier", while the cracks of the untreated specimens extended directly along the loading direction.

3.2 Macro- and Microstructural Changes

SEM identified a vitreous layer in mudstone and dense matrices in sandstone. XRD confirmed increased silica content post-irradiation. Saturated specimens exhibited larger pore volumes (CT) and cavitation blasting due to water-vapor interactions[4, 5].

3.3 CT scanning characteristics

The CT images were reconstructed and analyzed using Avizo software. The saturated specimens showed a larger pore volume compared to the dry specimens, which is related to water. For example, for the mudstone specimens, although the laser duration T2 of M-1-D was almost double that of M-4-W, the deeper burning cavity of the latter highlighted the water effect under irradiation. In addition, the assistance of high-pressure gas (such as in the case of M-10-W Laser 2) can form a deeper flared

cavity, which is because the high-pressure gas enables the rapid ejection of the molten rock.

4. Discussion

The study reveals that laser irradiation induces the melting of rock minerals through high temperature and high pressure, forming a molten glassy region. Micro-indentation tests have found that its hardness increases significantly compared with that of the original rock (for example, 1539.4 HV for sandstone vs. 785.6 HV). Under saturated conditions, the hydrothermal coupling effect promotes more intense vaporization and eruption, expanding the volume of the cavity.

The vitreous casing of certain thickness is constructed on the borehole inner wall through laser parameter adjustment and air-water assistance. This casing acts as a mechanical barrier to inhibit crack propagation and enhance borehole wall stability.

5. Conclusions

Laser irradiation enhances soft rock strength through phase evolution (e.g., quartz/silicate formation). Contrary to traditional water-weakening theories, saturated specimens exhibit superior mechanical performance due to vitrified layers and pore redistribution. Based on this, a technical solution is proposed to construct a high-strength vitreous casing on the inner wall of the borehole through the adjustment of laser parameters and the assistance of air and water. This work has demonstrated the wider applicability of laser irradiation not only for rock cracking but also for rock repair, which could point the way to the next generation of borehole stabilization technology.

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